

LIFE SAFETY SYSTEMS AND TYPES OF THE PEOPLE

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Security is the state of protection of the vital interests of the individual, society and the state from internal and external threats.

Main security systems:

- personal and collective human security;
- protection of the natural environment (biosphere);
- state (national) security;
- global security.

Personal security - the security of people, due to the individual qualities of the individual and the means of individual protection used. Collective (public) security is the security of people, due to the level of organization of state structures and the consciousness of people [1].

National security - the state of protection of national interests (constitutional system, sovereignty, territorial integrity of material and spiritual values).

At the heart of any security systems are personal and collective (public) security, which constitute the basic meaning of the concept of "life safety". Personal and collective security systems include the following main types of life safety:

– health security, which is understood as the somatic (bodily) norm of a person's condition, the normal functioning of all organ systems, taking into account age-related characteristics.

- psychological security, which implies the internal balance of a person, the adequacy of his reactions to external influences.
- social security, which means ensuring the protection of the most socially vulnerable segments of the population: children (eliminating child homelessness and crime), pensioners and the disabled, young mothers, large families (ensuring decent living conditions).
- anti-drug security, which in recent years has become one of the necessary conditions for the survival of the young generation exposed to drug danger.
- fire safety, which currently requires more and more attention due to: the inevitable dilapidation of the power grids of old residential buildings from time to time, the lack of funds for their planned replacement, the increasing power of electrical appliances connected to the network.
- technogenic (industrial and household) safety. In connection with the achievements of scientific and technological progress, man-made hazards are increasing, which are characteristic of many modern industrial enterprises. Unfortunately, despite all efforts for labor protection, the level of injuries and deaths at work cannot be reduced to zero, although this must be strived for.
- transport safety has become particularly important in recent years due to the increasing number of human casualties as a result of car accidents.
- natural and environmental safety.

A person is forced, on the one hand, to deal with dangers and threats of a natural nature (such as earthquakes, volcanic eruptions, floods, hurricanes, bites of poisonous snakes and insects, mushroom poisoning, colds and viral diseases), and on the other hand, to protect nature itself in in the course of environmental, environmental protection measures from predatory extermination of rare species of animals and plants, deforestation, poaching of fish, poisoning of water resources by wastewater from enterprises, destruction of the ozone layer of the atmosphere, etc[2].

The main subjects of ensuring these types of security on the part of the state and society itself are the bodies of the fire safety service, social security of internal affairs, health care, departments for combating drug trafficking and emergency situations, labor protection systems at enterprises, the state traffic safety inspectorate and etc.

The next level of security is state (national) security, which includes the following main types:

- anti-terrorist security is a system of effective protection of vital interests and the very existence of all security objects from the destructive forces of arbitrariness in any form of manifestation.
- demographic security provides for the optimal growth of the country's population, the creation of comfortable conditions for the existence of people in this country, an increase in their life expectancy, and ultimately, ensuring a high level of safety of their life.

The next level of security is the system of international collective security, which includes the following main types:

- anti-war security implies the active protection of the international community from the threat of unleashing large-scale armed conflicts, both between individual countries and within individual states[3].
- anti-epidemiological safety is connected with the system of protection of the international community from global epidemics (pandemics) of various deadly viral diseases through their prevention, worldwide epidemiological control and monitoring, modern vaccination of the population, etc.

Emergency situations are introduced in such epidemiological situations, and the Republic of Uzbekistan was not spared by such situations. In 2019, with the spread of the corona virus infection, a state of emergency was introduced in the Republic of Uzbekistan.

At the same time, during the past years, a state of emergency was declared in a number of countries due to the spread of the epidemic. In particular, in 2020 there will be a repeated state of emergency in several countries such as the USA, Albania, Armenia, Estonia, Georgia, Latvia, North Macedonia, Moldova, Romania, San Marino and Serbia, and in 2021 in Saitama, Chiba and Kanagawa prefectures of Japan, the Czech Republic and Latvia was introduced.

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